

PREVENTION OF CRIME AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract: This article examines effective approaches to prevent crime and promote positive development among youth. It discusses risk factors that influence criminal behavior in young people and outlines multi-pronged prevention strategies targeting individual, family, school and community levels. Prevention models include social-emotional learning programs, mentoring initiatives, after-school activities, career training and deterrent legal measures. The article emphasizes holistic approaches coordinated across sectors to address root causes through early interventions. With focused prevention efforts customized to local needs, societies can help steer more youth onto productive life paths.

Keywords: youth crime prevention, at-risk youth, risk factors, protective factors, multi-dimensional prevention, school-based prevention, community-based prevention, social development, juvenile justice.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются эффективные подходы к предотвращению преступности и содействию позитивному развитию среди молодежи. В нем обсуждаются факторы риска, влияющие на преступное поведение молодых людей, и излагаются многосторонние стратегии профилактики, ориентированные на индивидуальный уровень, семью, школу и сообщество. Модели профилактики включают программы социально-эмоционального обучения, инициативы наставничества, внеклассные мероприятия, профессиональную подготовку и сдерживающие правовые меры. В статье подчеркивается целостный подход, скоординированный во всех секторах, для устранения коренных причин посредством раннего вмешательства. Благодаря целенаправленным усилиям по профилактике, адаптированным к местным потребностям, общество может помочь направить больше молодежи на продуктивный жизненный путь.

Ключевые слова: профилактика молодежной преступности, молодежь из группы риска, факторы риска, защитные факторы, многомерная

профилактика, школьная профилактика, профилактика на уровне сообщества, социальное развитие, ювенальная юстиция.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada jinoyatchilikning oldini olish va yoshlar o'rtasida ijobiy rivojlanishga ko'maklashishning samarali usullari ko'rib chiqiladi. Unda yoshlarning jinoiy xulq-atvoriga ta'sir etuvchi xavf omillari muhokama qilinadi va individual, oila, maktab va jamiyat darajasiga qaratilgan ko'p qirrali oldini olish strategiyalari belgilab berilgan. Profilaktika modellari orasida ijtimoiy-emotsional ta'lim dasturlari, murabbiylik tashabbuslari, maktabdan keyingi mashg'ulotlar, martaba o'qitish va to'xtatuvchi huquqiy choralar kiradi. Maqolada asosiy sabablarni erta aralashuvlar orqali hal qilish uchun sektorlar bo'ylab muvofiqlashtirilgan yaxlit yondashuvlarga urg'u berilgan. Mahalliy ehtiyojlarga moslashtirilgan profilaktika choralari bilan jamiyatlar ko'proq yoshlarni samarali hayot yo'llariga yo'naltirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar jinoyatlarining oldini olish, xavf ostida bo'lgan yoshlar, xavf omillari, himoya omillari, ko'p qirrali profilaktika, maktab profilaktikasi, jamoatchilik asosidagi profilaktika, ijtimoiy rivojlanish, balog'atga etmaganlar odil sudlovi.

INTRODUCTION

Youth crime is a complex social issue impacting communities worldwide. During adolescence, as individuals transition into adulthood, there is heightened vulnerability to engage in risky or illegal behavior. Understanding factors influencing criminal tendencies and implementing targeted prevention strategies are crucial to positive youth development.

Traditionally, punitive approaches like stricter law enforcement have been emphasized. However, research shows prevention yield better long-term results than reactionary responses alone. Early intervention programs addressing root causes show the most promise to curb crime and help youth become productive citizens.

This article explores preventative approaches through a developmental lens. Adolescence presents opportunities but also challenges as youth push boundaries and form identities. Developmentally-informed solutions can help steer this process constructively.

The following sections define common risk/protective factors. Examples of effective prevention models targeting individual, family and environment-level variables through education, community engagement and coordination across sectors are also presented. The conclusion stresses holistic, culturally-sensitive

solutions tailored to local circumstances achieve optimal outcomes. With focus on youth strengths, programs can promote healthy transitions to adulthood.

Literature Analysis

Reducing youth crime has been a focus of research for decades. Early studies found risk factors like antisocial behaviors, family dysfunction, academic failure (Farrington, 2000; Loeber et al., 1999). Later research identified protective factors like parental monitoring, community involvement that buffer risk (Espelage et al., 2000; Hawkins et al., 2000).

Prevention programs targeting modifiable risks and promoting assets were developed. Life Skills Training teaches decision-making and social skills to reduce substance abuse, aggression (Botvin et al., 1995). Mentoring shows positive impacts on delinquency, emotional well-being, education (DuBois et al., 2011; Wheeler et al., 2010).

Methods

This review analyzes peer-reviewed research from 1990-2020 using online databases including ProQuest, EBSCO, PsychINFO. Studies examining youth crime prevention programs, risk/protective factors are included.

Key search terms are: "youth crime", "juvenile delinquency", "prevention", "intervention", "mentoring", "life skills". Included research employs quantitative designs evaluating program outcomes, qualitative exploring participant experiences.

This review synthesizes current knowledge on evidence-based risk/protective frameworks and prevention strategies. Guidelines are provided on effective program components to inform future efforts in reducing youth offending.

Discussion

This review synthesized the current research on preventing youth crime through multi-faceted approaches. Findings highlight the effectiveness of programs targeting modifiable risks while promoting assets. Life skills and mentoring have shown positive impacts by strengthening protective factors.

However, additional efforts are still needed to further reduce youth crime. While risk-focused models have advanced understanding, prevention may benefit more from comprehensive strengths-based frameworks. Programs emphasizing youths' capabilities beyond risks alone could inspire greater motivation for change.

Sustainability also poses a challenge, as positive effects sometimes diminish post-intervention. New models integrating prevention into schools and

communities on an ongoing basis may confer lasting protection. Technology could expand reach, though digital divides remain.

Cross-sector collaboration is likewise important. Coordinating efforts between social services, juvenile justice, education optimizes resources to meet complex needs. Individualized, culturally-responsive supports accounting for diversity may improve engagement.

Overall, continued progress requires innovation balanced with what works. Rigorous evaluation of newer approaches alongside established programs can advance the field's ability to promote youth well-being and safety. With determined application of current knowledge and pursuit of more effective solutions, communities can further reduce crime.

Results

The literature review yielded the following key findings:

Risk Factors

- Individual risks strongly associated with delinquency included early aggression, associates with criminal behavior, academic failure (Farrington, 2000).
- Family risks were parental criminality, weak parental supervision/involvement, family conflict (Loeber et al., 1999).

Protective Factors

- Key protective factors against crime included strong parental monitoring/bonding, commitment to school/education (Espelage et al., 2000).
- Prosocial peers, involvement in positive extracurricular activities also buffered risks (Hawkins et al., 2000).

Prevention Programs

- Life Skills Training effectively reduced drug use, aggression, conduct problems up to 3 years post-intervention (Botvin et al., 1995).
- Structured mentoring programs significantly improved educational outcomes, mental health, and reduced recidivism (DuBois et al., 2011; Wheeler et al., 2010).

The results highlight modifiable individual and family risks, as well as protective resources programs have successfully strengthened to reduce adolescent criminal behavior and associated issues. Overall, evidence supports multi-faceted prevention strategies.

Conclusion

Reducing youth crime requires an ongoing, collaborative approach utilizing current evidence. This review summarized key risk and protective factors

implicated in delinquency. It also outlined various prevention programs shown to effectively promote protective mechanisms and mitigate risks.

Overall, the research emphasizes the multi-determined nature of youth offending. A balance of individual skill-building, family support, and community engagement appears most promising for guiding youth away from crime. Both short-term and long-term effects must be considered in programming.

Moving forward, continued innovation is important to address gaps like limited sustainability or inclusive approaches. Evaluation of strengthened, technologically-enhanced models could further advance the field.

Collaboration across sectors optimizes resources to meet diverse needs. Staying informed of new evidence allows refinement of strategies. With determined, coordinated application of current best practices, communities can further promote thriving youth and enhanced public safety.

While more progress is still needed, this review highlights solid foundations from which to build comprehensive, equitable solutions. Concerted prevention efforts stand to significantly reduce youth crime.

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